

ATOM TRANSFER RADICAL (CO)POLYMERIZATION OF STYRENE MONOMERS BEARING CARBAZOLYL GROUP

Vaitusionak A.A.^{1,2}, Vasilenko I.V.¹, Kostjuk S.V.^{1,2}, Sych G.³, Tomkeviciene A.³,
Grazulevicius J.V.³

¹*Department of Chemistry, Belarusian State University, Minsk, Belarus,*

²*Research Institute for Physical Chemical Problems of the Belarusian State University, Minsk, Belarus*

³*Department of Polymer Chemistry and Technology, Kaunas University of Technology, Kaunas, Lithuania
vaitusionak@bsu.by*

Thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF) molecules have evolved as next-generation materials in organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) since they provide an approach to reach 100% internal quantum efficiency without use of noble metal elements [1]. TADF research has focused on small molecules that rely on vacuum-evaporation technologies [2]. However, TADF polymers suitable for simple, low-cost and easily scalable solution processability are less developed [3-4].

Herein we report the atom transfer radical (co)polymerization (ATRP) of carbazole-containing styrene derivatives, 9-(4-vinylphenyl)carbazole (M1) (Figure 1) and 9-(2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-4-vinylphenyl)carbazole (M2) (Figure 1) initiated by CuCl/N,N,N',N'',N''-pentamethyldiethylenetriamine (PMDETA)/ethyl 2-bromo-isobutyrate (EBiB) system in cyclohexanone at 90 °C for the first time.

Figure 1. Structures of monomers investigated in this work.

Homopolymerization of both monomers proceeds smoothly in a controlled fashion to afford complete monomer conversion in 4 h and 15 min for M1 and M2, respectively. The first-order plots are linear for both monomers. The synthesized polymers are characterized by relatively narrow molecular weight distribution ($M_w/M_n \leq 1.36$) and controlled molecular weights close to theoretical ones ($M_n = 1400-8600 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$). The obtained (co)polymers are characterized via NMR spectroscopy, size exclusion chromatography, differential scanning calorimetry, UV and fluorescence spectroscopies.

References:

- [1] Yang Z., Mao Z., Xie Z., Zhang Y., Liu S., et al. Chem. Soc. Rev. **46**, 915 (2017).
- [2] Wei Q., Fei N., Islam A., Lei T., Hong L., et al. Adv. Opt. Mater. **6**, 1800512 (2018).
- [3] Wei Q., Ge Z., Voit B. Macromol. Rapid Commun. **40**, 1800570 (2019).
- [4] Shao S., Hu J., Wang X., Wang L., et al. J. Am. Chem. Soc. **139**, 17739 (2017).

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823720.